

Supplemental information to: Self-reported preferences for Daylight Saving Time meet fundamentals of human physiology: correlations in the 2018 Public Consultation by the European Commission

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Keywords: observational studies; quantile regression; statistical modelling; bivariate regression; DST; summer time; society; latitude; sleep deprivation; spring transition; Europe; America; season

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1. TABULAR MATERIAL

Country	Latitude ϕ	Longitude λ	Time offset $Z - \lambda/\Omega$	Winter sunrise, SRW	Population P	Internet usage I
CY Cyprus	35.0°	33.4°	-0.22 h	7.18 h	864 236	84.43 %
MT Malta	35.9°	14.5°	0.04 h	7.22 h	475 701	81.66 %
GR Greece	38.1°	23.6°	0.42 h	7.33 h	10 741 165	72.24 %
PT Portugal	39.3°	-8.7°	0.58 h	7.39 h	10 291 027	74.66 %
ES Spain	40.4°	-3.6°	1.20 h	7.45 h	46 658 447	86.11 %
BG Bulgaria	42.7°	24.8°	0.35 h	7.58 h	7 050 034	64.78 %
IT Italy	43.7°	12.2°	0.19 h	7.64 h	60 483 973	74.39 %
HR Croatia	45.5°	16.1°	-0.07 h	7.75 h	4 105 493	75.29 %
RO Romania	45.6°	25.6°	0.29 h	7.76 h	19 533 481	70.68 %
SI Slovenia	46.2°	14.6°	0.03 h	7.79 h	2 066 880	79.75 %
HU Hungary	47.5°	19.0°	-0.27 h	7.89 h	9 778 371	76.07 %
FR France	47.8°	2.5°	0.84 h	7.91 h	67 026 224	82.04 %
AT Austria	48.0°	15.4°	-0.03 h	7.92 h	8 822 267	87.48 %
SK Slovakia	48.7°	18.7°	-0.25 h	7.98 h	5 443 120	80.45 %
LU Luxembourg	49.6°	6.1°	0.59 h	8.05 h	602 005	97.06 %
CZ Czech Republic	49.9°	15.4°	-0.02 h	8.07 h	10 610 055	80.69 %
BE Belgium	50.9°	4.4°	0.71 h	8.15 h	11 398 589	88.65 %
DE Germany	51.0°	9.3°	0.38 h	8.17 h	82 792 351	87.04 %
PL Poland	51.8°	19.3°	-0.28 h	8.23 h	37 976 687	77.54 %
NL Netherlands	52.1°	5.2°	0.66 h	8.26 h	17 181 084	91.89 %
GB United Kingdom	52.1°	-1.4°	0.09 h	8.26 h	66 273 576	90.69 %
IE Ireland	53.3°	-6.4°	0.43 h	8.38 h	4 830 392	87.00 %
LT Lithuania	54.9°	24.0°	0.40 h	8.55 h	2 808 901	79.72 %
DK Denmark	55.7°	11.6°	0.23 h	8.64 h	5 781 190	97.32 %
LV Latvia	56.9°	24.1°	0.39 h	8.80 h	1 934 379	83.58 %
SE Sweden	59.2°	15.8°	-0.05 h	9.12 h	10 120 242	89.25 %
EE Estonia	59.4°	24.8°	0.35 h	9.15 h	1 319 133	89.36 %
FI Finland	61.2°	24.9°	0.34 h	9.48 h	5 513 130	88.89 %

Table S1 The European Union Member States at the time of the 2018 public consultation with geographical coordinates: latitude ϕ , longitude λ , time offset —the difference between noon and midday, $Z - \lambda/\Omega$, where Z is the time zone offset and Ω is Earth’s rotation speed—, the winter sunrise time SRW (mean solar time), 2018 population numbers from Eurostat `demo_pjanind.tsv` table, and the internet usage from the World Bank <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/IT.NET.USER.ZS>.

Country	Q2 Cancel		Q2 Keep		Net $C - K$	Turnout $C + K$	Ratio C/K
	Absolute	C	Absolute	K			
CY Cyprus	3557	0.487 %	3951	0.541 % (3.5)	-0.054 %	1.029 %	0.900
MT Malta	625	0.161 %	537	0.138 %	0.023 %	0.299 %	1.164
GR Greece	15 829	0.204 %	20 443	0.263 %	-0.059 %	0.467 %	0.774
PT Portugal	29 045	0.378 %	5223	0.068 %	0.310 %	0.446 %	5.561
ES Spain	81 961	0.204 %	5971	0.015 %	0.189 %	0.219 %	13.727 (1.9)
BG Bulgaria	11 008	0.241 %	2123	0.046 %	0.195 %	0.288 %	5.185
IT Italy	15 464	0.034 %	7976	0.018 %	0.017 %	0.052 %	1.939
HR Croatia	19 493	0.631 %	2284	0.074 %	0.557 %	0.704 %	8.535
RO Romania	5827	0.042 %	1663	0.012 %	0.030 %	0.054 %	3.504
SI Slovenia	13 177	0.799 %	1911	0.116 %	0.683 %	0.915 %	6.895
HU Hungary	18 203	0.245 %	1952	0.026 %	0.218 %	0.271 %	9.325
FR France	328 124	0.597 %	64 497	0.117 %	0.479 %	0.714 %	5.087
AT Austria	200 160	2.594 % (4.7)	58 530	0.758 % (5.5)	1.835 % (3.0)	3.352 % (4.5)	3.420
SK Slovakia	26 435	0.604 %	6447	0.147 %	0.456 %	0.751 %	4.100
LU Luxembourg	8337	1.427 % (1.9)	2196	0.376 % (2.1)	1.051 %	1.803 % (1.7)	3.796
CZ Czech Republic	52 233	0.610 %	10 391	0.121 %	0.489 %	0.731 %	5.027
BE Belgium	52 267	0.517 %	10 143	0.100 %	0.417 %	0.618 %	5.153
DE Germany	2 633 311	3.654 % (7.3)	502 972	0.698 % (4.9)	2.956 % (5.6)	4.352 % (6.3)	5.236
PL Poland	121 668	0.413 %	6306	0.021 %	0.392 %	0.435 %	19.294 (3.5)
NL Netherlands	21 851	0.138 %	5948	0.038 %	0.101 %	0.176 %	3.674
GB United Kingdom	9582	0.016 %	2117	0.004 %	0.012 %	0.019 %	4.526
IE Ireland	10 205	0.243 %	1436	0.034 %	0.209 %	0.277 %	7.107
LT Lithuania	8744	0.390 %	833	0.037 %	0.353 %	0.428 %	10.497
DK Denmark	5042	0.090 %	1196	0.021 %	0.068 %	0.111 %	4.216
LV Latvia	6448	0.399 %	1146	0.071 %	0.328 %	0.470 %	5.627
SE Sweden	42 562	0.471 %	5815	0.064 %	0.407 %	0.536 %	7.319
EE Estonia	10 561	0.896 %	1868	0.158 %	0.737 %	1.054 %	5.654
FI Finland	50 288	1.026 %	2672	0.055 %	0.972 %	1.081 %	18.820 (3.3)
Median (all)		0.406 %		0.069 %	0.341 %	0.469 %	5.169
Average (w/o outliers)		0.393 %		0.074 %	0.330 %	0.486 %	4.969
Std dev (w/o outliers)		0.273 %		0.062 %	0.298 %	0.321 %	2.453
StdDev/Average		69 %		84 %	90 %	66 %	49 %
p -val normal (all)		0.02		0.01	0.06	0.03	0.08
p -val normal (w/o outliers)		0.60		0.48	0.89	0.82	0.58

Table S2 The results to question 2 in the 2018 public consultation conducted by the European Commission. Member States are listed in increasing values of latitude. Each answer to the question is given in absolute numbers and in shares of the target population $P \times I$. The net shares $C - K$, the turnout $C + K$ and the ratio C/K are shown. Tukey's fences ($k = 1.5$) were used to identify outliers, noted in blue ink. In parenthesis the distance to the third quartile in units of the interquartile range. The bottom rows display univariate descriptive statistics: the median value for the full set; the average, standard deviation and their ratio after outlier removal; the p -val of the null hypothesis "sample is normally distributed" for the full set and after removal of outliers.

Outcome	Pearson- R^2	p -val	Slope [95 % CI]	Unbiased SE	Outliers
<i>Predictor: Time offset</i>					
Cancel C	0.014	0.570		70 %	AT DE LU
Keep K	0.001	0.894		86 %	AT CY DE LU
Net $C - K$	0.005	0.732		92 %	AT DE
Turnout $C + K$	0.034	0.377		66 %	AT DE LU
Rate C/K	0.001	0.873		50 %	FI PL ES
<i>Predictor: SRW</i>					
Cancel C	0.177	0.036	0.185[0.013, 0.357]	64 %	AT DE LU
Keep K	0.030	0.420		85 %	AT CY DE LU
Net $C - K$	0.247	0.010	0.244[0.064, 0.424]	80 %	AT DE
Turnout $C + K$	0.057	0.252		66 %	AT DE LU
Rate C/K	0.239	0.013	2.248[0.517, 3.978]	44 %	FI PL ES

Table S3 The association between the geographical data (predictors) and the results to question 2 in the 2018 public consultation conducted by the European Commission. The null hypothesis fails to sustain for SRW and C , $C - K$, C/K and sustains for SRW and $C + K$. The null hypothesis always fails when time offset is the predictor. The unbiased standard error (SE) is scaled by the sample average value of the either outcome. The null hypothesis of normally distributed residuals sustained in every regression at the standard level of significance. The slopes are given in basis points per hour. The positive value shows larger shares of C , $C - K$ and C/K with higher SRW.

Country	Round	Sleep and other personal cares				Work			
		offset		midpoint		onset		midpoint	
		Local time	Distance to winter sunrise	Local time	Distance to winter sunrise	Local time	Distance to winter sunrise	Local time	Distance to winter sunrise
GR Greece	2	07:40h	-00:00h	04:10h	-03:30h	08:00h	+00:19h	12:40h	+04:59h
ES Spain	2	08:20h	-00:12h	04:20h	-04:12h	08:20h	-00:12h	13:00h	+04:27h
BG Bulgaria	1	07:10h	-00:39h	03:20h	-04:29h	08:00h	+00:10h	13:00h	+05:10h
IT Italy	2	07:30h	-00:16h	03:30h	-04:16h	08:00h	+00:13h	12:20h	+04:33h
RO Romania	2	07:20h	-00:37h	03:10h	-04:47h	08:00h	+00:02h	12:10h	+04:12h
SI Slovenia	1	06:50h	-00:53h	02:50h	-04:53h	07:00h	-00:43h	12:00h	+04:16h
HU Hungary	2	07:00h	-00:29h	02:50h	-04:39h	07:40h	+00:10h	12:00h	+04:30h
FR France	2	07:50h	-00:50h	03:40h	-05:00h	08:00h	-00:40h	13:20h	+04:39h
LU Luxembourg	2	07:40h	-00:51h	03:40h	-04:51h	08:00h	-00:31h	12:50h	+04:18h
BE Belgium	2	07:50h	-00:54h	03:40h	-05:04h	08:20h	-00:24h	12:50h	+04:05h
DE Germany	2	07:30h	-00:53h	03:20h	-05:03h	07:50h	-00:33h	12:10h	+03:46h
PL Poland	2	07:20h	-00:25h	03:00h	-04:45h	07:20h	-00:25h	12:20h	+04:34h
NL Netherlands	2	08:00h	-00:48h	03:50h	-04:58h	08:20h	-00:28h	13:00h	+04:11h
GB United Kingdom	2	07:50h	-00:26h	03:30h	-04:46h	08:30h	+00:13h	13:00h	+04:43h
LT Lithuania	1	07:00h	-01:49h	02:50h	-05:59h	07:40h	-01:09h	12:50h	+04:00h
LV Latvia	1	07:20h	-01:42h	03:10h	-05:52h	08:00h	-01:02h	13:20h	+04:17h
SE Sweden	1	07:30h	-01:17h	03:20h	-05:27h	07:50h	-00:57h	12:40h	+03:52h
EE Estonia	2	07:50h	-01:28h	03:40h	-05:38h	08:00h	-01:18h	12:50h	+03:31h
FI Finland	2	07:40h	-01:59h	03:30h	-06:09h	08:00h	-01:39h	12:30h	+02:50h

Table S4 The time marks associated with the sleep and other personal cares and the work cycles as per HETUS. Countries are listed in increasing values of latitude. The third left-most column list the round of HETUS: round 1 was taken around 2000; round 2 around 2010. Round 3 is currently in progress. Figure S3 shows the methodology to assess midpoints and offset/onset time marks.

Predictor	Pearson- R^2	p -val	Slope[95 % CI]	Unbiased SE
<i>Sleep and other personal cares offset</i>				
Distance to solar noon	0.007	0.751		80 %
Distance to SRW	0.447	0.003	-0.34[-0.55, -0.13]	59 %
<i>Work onset</i>				
Distance to solar noon	0.161	0.111		73 %
Distance to SRW	0.677	5×10^{-5}	-0.40[-0.56, -0.25]	45 %
<i>Sleep and other personal cares midpoint</i>				
Distance to solar noon	0.031	0.500		79 %
Distance to SRW	0.376	0.009	-0.27[-0.46, -0.08]	63 %
<i>Work midpoint</i>				
Distance to solar noon	0.001	0.918		80 %
Distance to SRW	0.474	0.002	-0.38[-0.60, -0.16]	58 %
Geographical predictors				
Time offset	0.000	0.960		80 %
SRW	0.384	0.008	0.29[0.09, 0.50]	63 %

Table S5 The association between time marks of human activity —measured through two distinct metrics— (predictor, see Table S4) and the shares of target population willing to cancel the time regulations as per the 2018 public consultation (outcome, see Table S2) in $N = 17$ Member States that reported Hetus statistics. Blue ink annotates p -values below the standard level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), which occurs only when predictors are measured relative to the winter sunrise. The negative slope shows that shares against the current regulations increases with earlier starting points relative to winter sunrise time. Slopes are given in basis points per hour. The unbiased standard error of the fit is scaled by sample average value of the fitted shares C (0.390 %) and the result expressed as a percentage. The null hypothesis of normally distributed residuals sustains in every regression at the standard level of significance. For comparison the association with geographical predictions in this subset is also shown.

2. ADDITIONAL FIGURES

Figure S1 An Albers projection of Europe with the countries participating in the 2018 public consultation on summertime arrangements (in shade and labeled). Dashed meridians annotate time meridians. Solid meridians annotate the boundaries of the physical time zones. Circles of latitudes annotate straight values of SRW, starting at SRW = 7.5 h (southern most) and ending at 9.5 h (northern most) in steps of 0.5 h. Color shades highlight time zones; from west to east, Western European Time ($Z = 0$), Central European Time ($Z = 1$ h) and Eastern European Time ($Z = 2$ h). Vertical bar annotates the quartile range of population weighted latitude at the median population weighted latitude. The black horizontal bar locates the population median latitude and longitude for the country, listed in Table S1. The map was made with Natural Earth, a free vector and raster map data available at <https://www.naturalearthdata.com/>.

Figure S2 The evolution of the seasonal factor F as a function of latitude ϕ . The seasonal factor is defined in Eq. (??) so that it equals to zero at the Equator. The seasonal factor gives the advance or delay of the sunrise and sunset times at the solstices relative to the Equatorial standard. The right axis shows the corresponding winter photoperiod (and the summer scotoperiod) $12\text{ h} - 2F(\phi)$. Data points annotate the Member States. The seasonal factor was modeled for a point-sized Sun and a refractionless atmosphere. The box expands from 30° to 50° and yields $F(\phi)$ from 1 h to 2 h. It is an educated guess for the utility range of seasonal regulations of time.

Figure S3 Determination of the midpoint and work onset. On the left panel the daily rhythm of labor as per HETUS. The area enclosed by the daily rhythm scales with the daily average total work. The shaded areas break even the total area. The hour of the day when this happens is the *midpoint* of the labor cycle. On the right panel, the maximum participation rate is halved. Work onset is determined as the hour of the day when the participation rate first exceeds the maximum daily participation rate. Similar analysis allow to assess the midpoint of the sleep/wake cycle and the sleep offset.

Figure S4 The association between the time offset —difference between noon and midday— and the shares of target population willing to cancel the regulations as per the 2018 public consultation C . Germany (3.18%), Austria (2.27%) and Luxembourg (1.38%) are not shown in the picture. The solid line shows the point estimates of the prediction; the dashed lines bound the 95% prediction interval. The null hypothesis “shares C do not depend on time offset” sustains ($p = 0.696$ at the standard level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), see Table S3 in the Supplemental Information. Labels show iso-3166 alpha-2 codes, see table S1.

Figure S5 The same as Figure 1B (main file) but in a magnified vertical scale to visualize the distribution of shares against the regulations.

Figure S6 The association between the winter sunrise time SRW and the net shares of population willing to abolish DST $C - K$ as per the 2018 public consultation C . The inset shows the distribution of shares scaled by the interquartile range to identify and quantify the outliers Austria, Germany, not shown in the main picture and excluded from the regression. The low quartile was $Q_1 = 0.085\%$ and the high quartile, $Q_3 = 0.522\%$ (see the boxplot on the left side of the plot). The solid line shows the point estimates of the prediction; the dashed lines bound the 95% prediction interval. The regression is statistically significant ($p = 0.010$) at the standard level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$). Notice that the span of the predictor is larger than one hour: the standard unit of social time and the size of the shift brought by DST to clocks. Horizontal bars highlight population weighted low and high quartiles (France and Spain show the span of the European areas only). Labels (iso-3166 alpha-2) in increasing values of latitude: CY Cyprus; MT Malta; GR Greece; PT Portugal; ES Spain; BG Bulgaria; IT Italy; HR Croatia; RO Romania; SI Slovenia; HU Hungary; FR France; AT Austria; SK Slovakia; LU Luxembourg; CZ Czech Republic; BE Belgium; DE Germany; PL Poland; GB United Kingdom; NL Netherlands; IE Ireland; LT Lithuania; DK Denmark; LV Latvia; SE Sweden; EE Estonia; FI Finland.

Figure S7 The association between the winter sunrise time SRW and the ratio of shares of population willing to cancel and to keep DST C/K as per the 2018 public consultation C . The results from the 2019 public consultation in Alberta (Canada) —permanent DST vs current regulations— are also shown. The inset shows the distribution of shares scaled by the interquartile range to identify and quantify the outliers Austria, Germany, not shown in the main picture and excluded from the regression. The low quartile was $Q_1 = 3.735$ and the high quartile, $Q_3 = 7.213$ (see the boxplot on the left side of the plot). The solid line shows the point estimates of the prediction; the dashed lines bound the 95% prediction interval. The regression is statistically significant ($p = 0.013$) at the standard level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$). Notice that the span of the predictor is larger than one hour: the standard unit of social time and the size of the shift brought by DST to clocks. Horizontal bars highlight population weighted low and high quartiles (France and Spain show the span of the European areas only). Labels (iso-3166 alpha-2) in increasing values of latitude: CY Cyprus; MT Malta; GR Greece; PT Portugal; ES Spain; BG Bulgaria; IT Italy; HR Croatia; RO Romania; SI Slovenia; HU Hungary; FR France; AT Austria; SK Slovakia; LU Luxembourg; CZ Czech Republic; BE Belgium; DE Germany; PL Poland; GB United Kingdom; NL Netherlands; IE Ireland; LT Lithuania; DK Denmark; LV Latvia; SE Sweden; EE Estonia; FI Finland.

Figure S8 The association between the winter sunrise time SRW and the turnout $C + K$ to question 2 from the 2018 public consultation. The inset shows the distribution of shares scaled by the interquartile range to identify and quantify the outliers Austria, Germany, not shown in the main picture and excluded from the regression. The low quartile was $Q_1 = 0.274\%$ and the high quartile, $Q_3 = 0.833\%$ (see the boxplot on the left side of the plot). The solid line shows the point estimates of the prediction; the dashed lines bound the 95% prediction interval. The regression is not statistically significant ($p = 0.252$) at the standard level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$). Notice that the span of the predictor is larger than one hour: the standard unit of social time and the size of the shift brought by DST to clocks. Horizontal bars highlight population weighted low and high quartiles (France and Spain show the span of the European areas only). Labels (iso-3166 alpha-2) in increasing values of latitude: CY Cyprus; MT Malta; GR Greece; PT Portugal; ES Spain; BG Bulgaria; IT Italy; HR Croatia; RO Romania; SI Slovenia; HU Hungary; FR France; AT Austria; SK Slovakia; LU Luxembourg; CZ Czech Republic; BE Belgium; DE Germany; PL Poland; GB United Kingdom; NL Netherlands; IE Ireland; LT Lithuania; DK Denmark; LV Latvia; SE Sweden; EE Estonia; FI Finland.

Figure S9 Scatter plots of the shares of target population willing to cancel DST as per the 2018 European Commission public consultation (outcome) vs two predictors related to human activity as per HETUS: midpoint of sleep to SRW (top) and midpoint of work to SRW (bottom). Circles refer to round 2 (year 2010) of HETUS, and squares to round 1 (year 2000). The null hypothesis “the predictor does not explain the outcome” does not sustain at the standard level of significance for either test. For midpoint of sleep $R^2 = 0.376, p = 0.009, N = 17$; for the midpoint of work $R^2 = 0.474, p = 0.002, N = 17$. Solid lines show the results of the linear regression; dashed lines bound the 95% prediction interval of the regression. Horizontal bars highlight population weighted low and high quartiles (France and Spain show the span of the European areas only). The null hypotheses sustained if the descriptor is set to distance to noon.